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Deliverables are additional outputs (e.g. information, special report, a technical diagram brochure, list, a software milestone or other building block of the action) that must be produced at a given moment during the action. A deliverable is an official report that provides enough information to the European Commission to ensure effective monitoring of the project.

The deadline is a statutory one, and we have to notify the project officer as soon as we know we are behind schedule, in the rarest situations where this is the case.

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Abstract

In line with the Horizon Europe (HE) policy on multi-actor research projects involving the agricultural community and interlinking EIP-AGRI and HE, FRUITDIV contributes for the co-creation and sharing of solutions/opportunities ready to participate to overall efforts aiming at conserving and using genetic resources in the EU.

The present deliverable (D7.6) includes the first set of practice abstracts developed during the first 18 months of the FRUITDIV project. A second set will be compiled by M30 and a third one by end of the project (M60).

All practice abstracts will be loaded to the CAP Network database and will be available at https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/practice-abstracts_en.

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1 Introduction

The list of practice abstracts included in this deliverable reads as follows:

- Using Field Book to streamline field data collection for fruit tree phenotyping
- Assessing biotic stress in wild apricot under low-input orchard conditions
- Standardising phenology scoring in wild apricot using BBCH scale and day-of-year system
- Using thermal imaging to assess drought resistance in wild apricot
- Monitoring phenology in pome fruit using BBCH stages and day-of-year values
- Evaluating rooting and grafting success in wild apricot for vegetative propagation
- Preparing apple tissues for metabolite analysis through freeze-drying and cryogenic grinding
- Quantifying polyphenols in apple tissues using targeted extraction and HPLC-MS
- Automating metabolite extraction in wild apricot for high-throughput analysis
- Using near-infrared spectroscopy for rapid leaf phenotyping in wild apricot

2 The first ten practice abstracts of the FRUITDIV project

Using Field Book to streamline field data collection for fruit tree phenotyping

The Field Book app is an open-source Android application (available on Google Play) designed to simplify and accelerate phenotypic data collection in field experiments, such as those in fruit tree orchards. Operators can use the app to import a pre-defined field matrix with unique plant identifiers and spatial information, configure up to sixteen trait types, and customise their trait list for a specific trial or a specific tree. Field Book enables real-time scoring in the orchard using simple touchscreen inputs, barcode scanning, and voice recording. All data is stored in structured formats and can be exported in wide or long table layouts, with filenames automatically capturing trial information and date. Photos taken through the app are linked to plant IDs and traits. The system reduces manual errors, allows time gains, maintains previous scoring history, and supports clean, structured exports for direct use in statistical softwares or databases like BrAPI (<https://brapi.org/>). It is particularly valuable for managing complex multi-trait assessments across large trials and for improving consistency and reproducibility in collaborative research networks. Users are advised to maintain consistent identifiers, export data regularly, and avoid changing trait settings mid-trial to ensure data integrity.

Assessing biotic stress in wild apricot under low-input orchard conditions

To assess resistance to pests and diseases in wild apricot orchards with low chemical input, a field protocol was developed based on visual estimation of damage. Observers can rapidly score (scoring 50 trees take 20 to 30 minutes only) the presence and severity of symptoms caused by monilia blossom blight, rust, shot hole, scab, mildew, corky spots on fruit, and aphids. Symptoms are scored at appropriate times during the season according to the type of symptom. For monilia blossom blight for instance, symptoms are scored after the blooming period and before full leaf extension. Each pest or disease is evaluated using percentage-based incidence and severity scales adapted to symptom type. For instance, rust and shot hole are scored based on how many leaves show symptoms and how much of each leaf is affected. Scores are converted to percentages to enable consistent analysis. Aphid presence is rated based on colony size and coverage. All scoring is designed for use under natural infection, reflecting real orchard conditions and allowing comparison across genotypes and environments. The approach supports breeders and curators of germplasm repository in identifying resilient plant material for low-input systems.

Standardising phenology scoring in wild apricot using BBCH scale and day-of-year system

This protocol enables harmonised phenotyping of key developmental stages in wild apricot by recording all observations as day-of-year (DOY) values using the BBCH scale (the abbreviation BBCH derives from the first letters of the German names of **B**iologische Bundesanstalt (Federal Biological Research Centre), **B**undessortenamt (Federal Plant Variety Office) and **C**hemical industry). Bolting (BBCH 10-11), blooming (BBCH 65), and maturity (BBCH 87) dates are monitored regularly to capture variation among genotypes. Blooming is tracked through three reference points: the start (10%

flowers open), mid-flowering (50%), and full bloom (100%), with data collected up to three times a week for accuracy. Flower density is rated on a scale from 0 to 5 at full bloom (100%). Flower necrosis is scored by touching branches to observe dried, undeveloped flower buds falling down. Flower abnormalities are recorded by shaking branches to manually identify the absence, necrosis, or malformation of pistils. Flower damage from frost is also documented visually during the flowering period. Maturity is scored based on fruit ripeness for commercial harvest, assessed through weekly visits. This structured and repeatable approach supports comparative studies and breeding for phenological traits under varying climatic conditions.

Using thermal imaging to assess drought resistance in wild apricot

This method evaluates drought resistance in wild apricot by measuring leaf temperature with a hand held infra-red radiometric camera, which indirectly reflects transpiration and stomatal conductance. Trees are monitored under both well-watered and water-limited conditions by observing soil water content. Images are taken between late morning and early afternoon using a calibrated infra-red radiometric camera positioned at a fixed distance and angle. A wet and a dry reference surface are included in the frame to standardise readings. The canopy temperature is extracted from thermal images according to differences between the wet and dry reference surface. The canopy temperature is used to calculate indices such as the crop water stress index (CWSI) and an index of stomatal conductance (lg). These indices help distinguish between genotypes with high or low water loss through transpiration under stress. By capturing plant responses at water stress conditions, this non-invasive method enables rapid screening of large populations, aiding in the selection of drought-resilient varieties suited to climate change.

Monitoring phenology in pome fruit using BBCH stages and day-of-year values

This protocol provides a harmonised method to monitor phenological stages in wild apple and pear by combining the BBCH scale with day-of-year (DOY) notation. The BBCH scale (*Biologische Bundesanstalt, Bundessortenamt und Chemische Industrie*) is a universal system used to describe the growth and development stages of plants in a consistent and detailed way. Rather than relying on vague terms like “flowering” or “ripening,” it breaks a plant’s life cycle down into clearly defined stages, each assigned a specific numerical code. Each stage is described using a two-digit code: the first digit refers to the main phase of development (like germination, flowering, or fruit ripening), while the second digit offers a more detailed view of progress within that phase.

Observations focus on bud burst, flowering, fruit maturity and leaf fall, allowing for detailed comparison across genotypes and environments. Bud burst is recorded when green tips enclosing the flower become visible, while flowering is tracked in three stages: beginning (10% flowers open), full flowering (50%) and end of flowering (all petals fallen). Flowering intensity is scored on a 0 to 9 scale. Fruit maturity is recorded using the BBCH 87 stage when fruit is ripe for picking, and leaf senescence is tracked through stages of discolouration and complete leaf fall. Regular observations, usually twice weekly, ensure precision. This approach supports breeding and conservation by capturing genotypic variability in response to seasonal and climatic conditions.

Evaluating rooting and grafting success in wild apricot for vegetative propagation

This protocol enables the assessment of rooting and grafting potential in wild apricot, supporting the selection of genotypes suitable for vegetative propagation. For rooting, cuttings are taken in winter, treated with fungicide, and dipped in indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) to enhance root induction. After storage in controlled conditions, they are planted in a peat–perlite mix and monitored for sprouting and root formation. Rooting is evaluated by the number of roots and the presence of callus tissue. For grafting, one-year-old rootstocks are chip-budded with scions, and the union is secured and observed after three months for compatibility traits such as graft take, length and anatomical integrity. Sections of the graft interface are examined microscopically and scored for tissue organisation, from full integration to incompatibility. This dual method provides a comprehensive picture of the propagation potential of different genotypes and helps identify those most suited to conservation, orchard use or breeding programs.

Preparing apple tissues for metabolite analysis through freeze-drying and cryogenic grinding

To ensure high-quality and reproducible results in metabolite analysis of apple tissues, this protocol standardises sample preparation through lyophilisation and cryogenic grinding. Fresh leaf or fruit samples are sliced, rapidly frozen in liquid nitrogen, and ground into a fine powder to preserve chemical integrity. The powdered material is transferred into pre-chilled tubes and either stored at -80°C or processed directly. For long-term stability and ease of handling, the samples undergo freeze-drying in a vacuum lyophiliser, typically over 24 to 48 hours. The drying setup uses perforated parafilm to avoid contamination while allowing moisture to escape. Once dry, the material is sealed in airtight containers to prevent rehydration. This procedure minimises enzymatic degradation and preserves the native metabolite profile, providing a stable and homogenous starting point for further biochemical or molecular analyses in apple research. This protocol can be used for any fruit plant.

Quantifying polyphenols in apple tissues using targeted extraction and HPLC-MS

This protocol enables precise quantification of phenolic compounds in apple tissues through a two-step extraction process followed by high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS). Lyophilised samples are extracted with a water, methanol and chloroform mixture, followed by a second methanol–water extraction to improve compound recovery. After centrifugation, the combined supernatants are filtered and stored at -20°C . For analysis, a small sample volume is injected into a UPLC system connected to a tandem mass spectrometer operating in electrospray ionisation mode. A predefined solvent gradient allows separation of phenolic compounds, which are detected through multiple reaction monitoring. The method ensures high sensitivity, specificity and reproducibility, allowing for detailed metabolite profiling. It is particularly suitable for comparing polyphenol content among genotypes or treatments in breeding, quality assessment, or stress-response studies.

Automating metabolite extraction in wild apricot for high-throughput analysis

This protocol describes an automated approach to extract metabolites from lyophilised wild apricot tissues using a robotic liquid handling system, enabling high-throughput and standardised sample processing. A solvent mix containing ethanol, formic acid and an internal standard is added to finely ground material at cold temperatures. Samples are shaken, sonicated in ice water, and centrifuged to recover the extract. The process is repeated to ensure full recovery, and the combined supernatant is filtered using a second robot-assisted step. A quality control mix is prepared by pooling equal volumes from all extracts to monitor consistency. Extracts are stored at -20°C before analysis. This system reduces human error and increases reproducibility, making it ideal for large-scale metabolomics, both targeted and untargeted. It supports precise biochemical characterisation of genotypes under different environmental or developmental conditions.

Using near-infrared spectroscopy for rapid leaf phenotyping in wild apricot

This protocol allows rapid, non-destructive measurement of wild apricot leaf traits using a portable near-infrared spectrometer directly in the orchard (device available at <https://www.portableas.com/analytical-spectral-devices/qualityspec-trek/>). Fresh leaves are collected from consistent positions within the canopy to minimise variability due to light exposure or height. The adaxial side of each leaf is placed against the spectrometer window, and a magnetic clip is used to stabilise the sample during scanning. Each scan collects a spectrum across the 350–2500 nm range, with multiple scans averaged per sample. The device records both spectral data and sample identification numbers, enabling easy traceability. This method facilitates the collection of large datasets suitable for calibration models to predict physiological or biochemical traits, such as water status, pigment content or metabolite concentrations. Its speed and portability make it well suited to screening large populations for functional traits in field conditions.